

The Pyramid Texts: Pyramid of King Unas (Wnjs)

By Brendan Hainline, University of Chicago

Entry tags: Ancient Egyptian Text, Egyptian Religions, Mortuary text, Tomb, Religious Group, Text

The Pyramid Texts is a modern name given to an Egyptian corpus of entextualized ritual utterances and religious texts that were inscribed on the walls within the burial chambers of royal pyramids in the later Old Kingdom. The corpus was fluid, altogether containing over 800 Pyramid Texts—individually called “utterances” or “spells”—although no source contains every Pyramid Text utterance. The purpose of the Pyramid Texts as a whole was to ensure that the deceased passed safely into the afterlife to become an akh (ꜥḫ), or “effective spirit.” A large number of the ritual utterances in the corpus focus upon this transfiguration. Other utterances in the corpus represent mortuary and offering rituals, hymns to important deities, and apotropaic rituals for the protection of the tomb and the deceased. This diversity of textual genres of utterances are evidence that the Pyramid Texts were compiled in part from diverse, pre-existing textual (and likely oral) sources. While many of the utterances originated in rituals composed and practiced specifically with the king as beneficiary, others have been demonstrated to have non-royal origins. This illustrates that the ancient editors of the corpus—likely high ranking priests and religious officials—drew upon a number of different sources when deciding which specific rituals and religious texts to incorporate into the Pyramid Texts corpus. The first attested Pyramid Texts are in the tomb of King Unas (Wnjs, alternately romanized as Unis or Wenis), the last king of the Fifth Dynasty. The Pyramid Texts of King Unas are the best preserved of the Old Kingdom sources, but also only contain 226 of the ~800 total Pyramid Text utterances. The Fifth Dynasty was a time of great religious change during which the god Osiris (Wsjr) first appears in Egyptian religion. It is in the Pyramid Texts of Unas that Osiris first appears in a royal context. After King Unas, the Pyramid Texts continued to be inscribed in the burial chambers of the pyramids of Sixth Dynasty kings, as well as some Sixth Dynasty queens. These later Old Kingdom sources added additional utterances and subtracted some as well, such that no two individuals’ tombs included the same repertoire of utterances. Although restricted to royal burials during the Old Kingdom, the Pyramid Texts were later revived and re-used throughout ancient Egyptian history in the tombs of non-royal individuals. Some utterances of the Pyramid Texts were also adopted into later mortuary corpora, including the Coffin Texts and the Book of the Dead.

Date Range: 2375 BCE - 2345 BCE

Region: Pyramid of Unas

Region tags: Middle East, Africa, Egypt

Pyramid of Unas at Saqqara

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Sethe, Kurt. 1908-1912. Die altaegyptische Pyramidentexte nach den Papierabdrucken und

Photographien des Berliner Museums. 4 volumes. Leipzig: J. C. Hinrichs.

- Source 2: Allen, James P. 2015. *The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid Texts*. *Writings from the Ancient World* 38. Atlanta: SBL Press.
- Source 3: Piankoff, Alexandre. 1968. *The Pyramid of Unas: Texts translated with commentary by A. Piankoff*. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ancientworldonline.blogspot.com/2013/07/a-new-concordance-of-pyramid-texts.html>
- Source 1 Description: *A New Concordance of the Pyramid Texts*, by James P. Allen

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: http://www3.lib.uchicago.edu/cgi-bin/eos/eos_title.pl?callnum=PJ1553.A1_1908
- Source 1 Description: Online scans of Sethe, Kurt. 1908-1912. *Die altaegyptische Pyramidentexte nach den Papierabdrucken und Photographien des Berliner Museums*. 4 volumes. Leipzig: J. C. Hinrichs.
- Source 1 URL: <https://aaew.bbaw.de/tla/servlet/OTPassport?u=guest&f=0&l=0&oc=21149&db=0>
- Source 1 Description: The texts from the Pyramid of Unis in the *Thesaurus Linguae Aegyptiae* (sign in required).

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Method of inscription

- Chisel

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Stone

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The stone was worked into smooth masonry on which the texts could be inscribed.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The Pyramid Texts of Unas were compiled together from multiple sources, some of which were rituals to be recited by the beneficiary (i.e. the text was in first person). These first-person utterances were largely edited to be third-person, with the name of King Unas (or a third-person pronoun) inserted.

Reference: Hays, Harold M.. *The Organization of the Pyramid Texts: Typology and Disposition*. Brill, 2012. p.12, p.138-158

Reference: Morales, Antonio J.. "Text-building and Transmission of Pyramid Texts in the Third Millennium BCE: Iteration, Objectification, and Change". *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 15, no. 2 (2016): 169-201.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– Yes

↳ Cemetery

– Yes

Notes: The pyramid of King Unas is part of the larger cemetery of Saqqara, which also contains a number of other royal pyramids, some of which also contain Pyramid Texts.

↳ Temple

– Field doesn't know

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– Yes

Notes: In the sense that a pyramid is a funerary monument.

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No

↳ Cave(s)
– No

↳ Hilltops
– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries
– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines
– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

↳ Specify

– Specify: The Pyramid Texts are inscribed upon the stone walls of the burial chambers (sarcophagus chamber, antechamber, and descending passage) of King Unas. We know that there were also hieratic copies of the Pyramid Texts, probably written on papyrus, kept somewhere other than the tomb such as in a temple or royal archive. These would have been used as references for the later tombs that contained Pyramid Texts. However, we do not know where these papyri were kept.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: In the Sarcophagus Chamber of the Pyramid of Unas, in addition to Pyramid Texts, the "palace façade" motif is carved on the walls directly surrounding the royal sarcophagus.

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Religious space with restricted access

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: We don't have direct evidence of who the authors/copyists/engravers of the Pyramid Texts of Unas were, but since the texts are located within the King's tomb, the creators of the texts were almost certainly provided for by the royal court/state.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The king and state would have been responsible for the construction of King Unas's pyramid, and thus also the Pyramid Texts within. As King Unas is the first king to have Pyramid Texts within his tomb, he is undoubtedly responsible for the initial compilation and construction of the corpus. The commission of specific new Pyramid Texts for the tomb of King Unas (as opposed to the ritual utterances compiled from pre-existing ritual sources) is likely, but is as yet speculation.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Notes: No legal code existed in Old Kingdom Egypt.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We don't know specifically which literate priests were responsible for the creation of ritual texts. There is evidence that some priests only worked in certain months of the year, and held other positions and jobs in the other months.

↳ Present part-time?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there were both male and female priests in the Old Kingdom, because we do not know which priests were responsible for the creation of ritual texts, we cannot say much about the gender of the editors/creators of the Pyramid Texts.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Yes

Notes: The priests in charge of producing the Pyramid Texts would have been Egyptian.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– No

Notes: We have no evidence for this in the Old Kingdom.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious

specialists?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many of the individual utterances of the Pyramid Texts likely came from an oral tradition. However, we don't have any direct evidence of or contemporary references to this.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Yes

Notes: No two pyramids in the Old Kingdom use the same selection of Pyramid Text utterances.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: The editors of the Pyramid Texts were likely literate priests, and so would have received instruction of some kind in reading and writing hieroglyphs. However, we have no clear information about who these priests were.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to say what the "audience" of these texts were, as they are inscribed on the walls of the sealed king's tomb. Likely only select craftsmen and priests would have seen the monumental inscriptions themselves before the tomb was sealed. However, many of the individual ritual utterances were adapted from broadly used, non-royal rituals. So individual utterances of the Pyramid Texts had a wide audience (in their pre-monumentalization history of use).

Reference: Baines, John. "Restricted Knowledge, Hierarchy, and Decorum: Modern Perceptions and Ancient Institutions". *Journal of the American Research Center in Egypt* 27 (n.d.). p.31

Reference: Morales, Antonio J.. "From Voice to Papyrus to Wall: Verschriftung and Verschriftlichung in the Old Kingdom Pyramid Texts". In *Understanding Material Text Cultures: A Multidisciplinary View*, edited by Markus Hilgert, 69-130. De Gruyter, 2016.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The Pyramid Text corpus is a compilation of entextualized utterances in part collected and compiled from pre-existing ritual sources. However, the texts once monumentalized on the walls of the burial chambers were not themselves read in a funerary or mortuary ritual.

↳ Is it orally recited?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it read?
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some of the rituals utterances would have been read from hieratic documents, while some might have been orally recited. But, this would have been before the utterances were entextualized and monumentalized. The rituals would not have been performed by reading the texts on the wall of the subterranean chambers of the pyramid.

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
– Specify: Many of the utterances of the Pyramid Texts seem to reflect rituals that were mortuary/funerary in nature, but others, such as the apotropaic rituals against snakes, could have had broader use for living individuals.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many of the Pyramid Texts, specifically those of the Offering Ritual (PT 23-244), involve the presentation of food and drink offerings to the deceased. Whether or not these offerings were then fully or partially consumed by the offerers is not clear from the texts.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Notes: The Pyramid Texts are clearly visible on the walls of the king's tomb when one is in the tomb. However, after his death the tomb would have been sealed and the texts would therefore be hidden.

↳ Is it hidden?

– Yes

Notes: The Pyramid Texts are clearly visible on the walls of the king's tomb when one is in the tomb. However, after his death the tomb would have been sealed and the texts would therefore be hidden.

↳ Can it be touched?

– No

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Yes

Notes: Many of the individual utterances of the Pyramid Texts are apotropaic texts (for example, PT 226-243). These texts in particular ward off snakes and snake-like supernatural creatures.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– No

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– No

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

Notes: In later periods, Egyptian mortuary texts (including some re-used Pyramid Texts) were freely written on wooden coffins, papyrus, or in other masonry tombs.

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The Pyramid Texts do not have any of the associated images common in the later Egyptian Book of the Dead and Underworld Books.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Each royal pyramid of the Old Kingdom that contained Pyramid Texts inscribed on the walls of their burial chambers contained a unique set of utterances. There was significant overlap between pyramids, but no two sources share the same repertoire of inscribed utterances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Pyramid Texts of King Unas only contain 226 of the ~800 total Pyramid Text utterances. The rest are present in royal tombs of the following Sixth Dynasty kings.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The Egyptians have a long tradition of mortuary literature that starts with the Pyramid Texts. In the First Intermediate Period, the Coffin Texts first appear (and re-use some of the Pyramid Texts). In the New Kingdom, the Book of the Dead appears (which also re-uses some Pyramid Texts).

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The Pyramid Texts record the utterances that would have been spoken during the rituals. The actual instructions of the rituals, i.e. which actions to perform and which ritual implements/offerings to manipulate during the ritual, are only recorded in the Offering Texts (PT 23-170 and others).

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The ancient Egyptians in the Old Kingdom when the Pyramid Text corpus was created had more nuanced beliefs than a simple spirit-body duality. They believed that every person had a body and then two immaterial elements: (1) a ka (kꜣ), which is sometimes translated unhelpfully as "double" and seems to be something like a person's life-force; and (2) a ba (bꜣ), which has more to do with the person's individuality and self. If the ka and the ba were re-united in the afterlife, then that person became an akh (ꜣḫ), an "effective" or "luminous" spirit.

Reference: Allen, James P.. The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid Texts. SBL Press, 2015. p.7-9

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: The ancient Egyptians in the Old Kingdom when the Pyramid Text corpus was created had more nuanced beliefs than a simple spirit-body duality. They believed that every person had a body and then two immaterial elements: (1) a ka (kꜣ), which is sometimes translated unhelpfully as "double" and seems to be something like a person's life-force; and (2) a ba (bꜣ), which has more to do with the person's individuality and self. If the ka and the ba were reunited in the afterlife, then that person became an akh (ꜣḫ), an "effective" or "luminous" spirit.

Reference: Allen, James P.. *The Ancient Egyptian Pyramid Texts*. SBL Press, 2015. p.7–9

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Field doesn't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Pyramid Texts do not present a unified view of the afterlife. This is because the texts were compiled from a number of different sources and traditions. The afterlife was in the sky and was viewed as a watery, marshy land filled with lakes and canals. It was reached by ladder (PT 271, PT 305, PT 306) or by ferry (PT 270, PT 300, PT 310). The afterlife region was sometimes specifically called the Duat (Dwꜣt).

Reference: Zago, Silvia. *A Journey Through the Beyond*. Lockwood Press, 2022.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: The Pyramid Texts do not present a unified view of the afterlife. This is because the texts were compiled from a number of different sources and traditions. The afterlife was in the sky and was viewed as a watery, marshy land filled with lakes and canals. It was reached by ladder (PT 271, PT 305, PT 306) or by ferry (PT 270, PT 300, PT 310). The afterlife region was sometimes specifically called the Duat (Dwꜣt).

Reference: Zago, Silvia. *A Journey Through the Beyond*. Lockwood Press, 2022.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: While the deceased was thought to be "alive" in the afterlife ("You have not gone away being dead, you have gone away being alive," PT 213), reincarnation into the world of the living was not believed in.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

Notes: The Offering Texts reference material offerings that would have been presented to King Unas during the funerary ritual and as grave goods. It is not clear whether these texts represent the actual offerings that would have been presented or rather a list of possible offerings. Because the tomb of Unas was looted in antiquity, we do not know what grave goods were included when he was buried.

↳ Personal effects?

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Yes

↳ Significant value? (Gold, jade, so forth)

– Yes

↳ Some value? (valuable, or useful objects)

– Yes

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: While there are several Pyramid Text utterances (PT 534, PT 599, PT 600, PT 601) that reference the burial of the king in a pyramid and invoke protection for the pyramid, none of these are present in the corpus of King Unas. They were added into the Pyramid Text corpus later, during the reign of King Pepy I.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Unas's pyramid, and other pyramids of the late Old Kingdom that also contain Pyramid Texts, have large mortuary temple complexes attached. These complexes were used in the mortuary cults of the deceased kings, and many of the rituals represented in the Pyramid Texts, especially the Offering Rituals, would have taken place in these temples.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: Unas's pyramid, and other pyramids of the late Old Kingdom that also contain Pyramid Texts, have large mortuary temple complexes attached. These complexes were used in the mortuary cults of the deceased kings, and many of the rituals represented in the Pyramid Texts, especially the Offering Rituals, would have taken place in these temples.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: The idea of an Egyptian supreme high god isn't really present in the Old Kingdom. The sun-god Ra (Rr) is very important, but does not yet fill the role of a "supreme" god like the god Amun-Ra does in the New Kingdom.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Notes: Some of the Pyramid Texts of Unas (PT 217, PT 218, PT 269) refer to the deceased becoming one of the J.ḥmw-sk, the "Imperishable Stars" (literally, "The Ones Who Do Not Know Perishing"). These are the circumpolar stars, those stars near the North Star (Polaris) that can be seen throughout the year. So in this case, yes the deceased's spirit, having become a star, can be seen. *Note: The deceased becoming an Imperishable Star occurs in additional Pyramid Texts that do not occur in Unas's corpus.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not explicitly stated in the Pyramid Texts. However, as the deceased received offerings at the time of their burial and continued to be the beneficiary of a mortuary cult, we can assume that the deceased's "spirit" continued to be aware of what was happening in the world of the living, at least in the vicinity of their tomb.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The deceased continues to "rule" over the living in a manner similar to the gods. This motif is present in PT 213, PT 221, PT 224, and PT 225 (as well as additional utterances not present in the corpus of King Unas). This rulership is often expressed by saying that the deceased's "scepter" is in front of the living.

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

Notes: As said above, the deceased continued to "rule" over the living. This includes making decrees (wđ mdw) to the living/mankind (PT 213 and PT 252). The exact manner of how these decrees were received by the living is not explicitly stated.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch

– Field doesn't know

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Not a lot of specifics are given, but supernatural beings - know about offerings made to them (PT 215) - know about the deceased beneficiary of the ritual (PT 262, PT 726)

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

Notes: Usually, the deceased is said to continue to rule ("issue decrees," etc.) to the living (see above), and is put in this position by the gods. In this way, the deceased acts as an intermediary between the gods and living humans.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The king in the Old Kingdom (and later) was believed to be partially divine. Starting in the Fourth Dynasty, king's would put the modifier "son of Ra" before their Birth Name in their titulary. Additionally, there are several times in the Pyramid Texts where Unas is said to be the son of one god or another: - son of Atum (PT 215, PT 216, PT 222) - son of Ra (PT 205, PT 222, PT 271) - son of Osiris (PT 303, PT 310) - son of Geb (PT 214, PT 254) - son of Ra-Atum (PT 217) - son of Sopdet (Sothis) (PT 302) - son of Hathor (PT 303) - son of Neith (PT 317) *Note that kingship terms in Old Egyptian do not distinguish between "son" and "grandson," "father" and "grandfather," or "mother" and "grandmother." Therefore some of these relations may actually reflect a distance of more than one generation.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, the king himself was a (semi-)divine being.

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– Yes

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Several of the apotropaic rituals attested in the Pyramid Texts ward off snakes, both natural and supernatural. While not attested in the corpus of Unas, later kings' pyramids include texts that mention a class of beings called ḥꜣtꜣw, which has been translated as "demons of slaughter."

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: A major function of the rituals of the Pyramid Texts is to aid the deceased in becoming an akh (ꜣḫ), an "effective spirit." Many deities and lesser divine beings are evoked in the rituals to assist the deceased in this "akh-ification."

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Notes: A few Pyramid Texts (PT 436, PT 665, PT 665C) mention the presence of pleasing scents – probably a reference to incense offerings for the deceased.

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

Notes: Eternal happiness is by no means a major theme in the Pyramid Texts, but the concept does appear a few times. The Egyptian idiom for happiness is 3w(j) jb "to be long of heart." The deceased is happy in the Afterlife in PT 408 and PT 511. A similar concept would be htp "(be) content, (be) at peace." This idea of contentment is much more common in the Pyramid Texts.

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

Notes: As above, a goal of the Pyramid Texts is the transfiguration of the deceased into an akh (3ḥ) "effective spirit" in the Afterlife. This does not seem to be a full "reincarnation."

↳ Other?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

Notes: The Offering Texts within this corpus include offerings of meat, but there is no indication that the animal was sacrificed rather than butchered elsewhere.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Pyramid Texts of Unas includes 126 utterances that are written statements that would have been spoken aloud during the performed Offering Ritual. Whether every one of these utterances was mandatory to be performed during the Offering Ritual – or if they form a large bank from which specific rites could be recited as needed – is unclear.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– Yes

Notes: There would have been mortuary offerings included in the tomb, but they were looted in antiquity.

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Yes

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A state

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Saqqara

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: While there were women in Egypt who could read and write, and there were priestesses who would have performed rituals, the majority of ancient Egyptians who received education (and thus were literate) were men.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Other [specify]: The Pyramid Texts of Unas were compiled together from multiple sources, some of which were rituals to be recited by the beneficiary (i.e. the text was in first person). These first-person utterances were largely edited to be third-person, with the name of King Unas (or a third-person pronoun) inserted., Hays, Harold M.. *The Organization of the Pyramid Texts: Typology and Disposition*. Brill, 2012. p.12, p.138-158

Reference: Other [specify]: The Pyramid Texts of Unas were compiled together from multiple sources, some of which were rituals to be recited by the beneficiary (i.e. the text was in first person). These first-person utterances were largely edited to be third-person, with the name of King Unas (or a third-person pronoun) inserted., Morales, Antonio J.. "Text-building and Transmission of Pyramid Texts in the Third Millennium BCE: Iteration, Objectification, and Change". *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 15, no. 2 (2016): 169-201.

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